

Novel approaches for the rapid development of rationally designed arbovirus vaccines

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ABSTRACT

Vector-borne diseases, including those transmitted by mosquitoes, account for more than 17% of infectious diseases worldwide. This number is expected to rise with an increased spread of vector mosquitoes and viruses due to climate change and man-made alterations to ecosystems. Among the most common, medically relevant mosquito-borne infections are those caused by arthropod-borne viruses (arboviruses), especially members of the genera *Flavivirus* and *Alphavirus*. Arbovirus infections can cause severe disease in humans, livestock and wildlife. Severe consequences from infections include congenital malformations as well as arthritogenic, haemorrhagic or neuroinvasive disease. Inactivated or live-attenuated vaccines (LAVs) are available for a small number of arboviruses; however there are no licensed vaccines for the majority of these infections. Here we discuss recent developments in pan-arbovirus LAV approaches, from site-directed attenuation strategies targeting conserved determinants of virulence to universal strategies that utilize genome-wide re-coding of viral genomes. In addition to these approaches, we discuss novel strategies targeting mosquito saliva proteins that play an important role in virus transmission and pathogenesis in vertebrate hosts.

For rapid pre-clinical evaluations of novel arbovirus vaccine candidates, representative *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental systems are required to assess the desired specific immune responses. Here we discuss promising models to study attenuation of neuroinvasion, neurovirulence and virus transmission, as well as antibody induction and potential for cross-reactivity. Investigating broadly applicable vaccination strategies to target the direct interface of the vertebrate host, the mosquito vector and the viral pathogen is a prime example of a One Health strategy to tackle human and animal diseases.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the frequency, magnitude and global distributions of arthropod-borne (arbo)virus outbreaks have been fuelled by changes in climate, urbanization, human migration and population growth [1–7]. Increasing arbovirus prevalence can be ascribed to the expansion of mosquito vector populations, improved transmission efficiency and the adaptation of viruses to new host and vector species. Examples of important arbovirus (re-)emergence include the continuous global

spread of dengue virus (DENV) and West Nile virus (WNV) and large outbreaks of chikungunya virus (CHIKV) and Zika virus (ZIKV) in the southern hemisphere [8–10]. Infection with these arboviruses can cause severe disease including congenital malformations as well as arthritogenic, haemorrhagic or neuroinvasive disease. Arboviruses may also infect livestock and wildlife, creating an animal reservoir that increases the chances of zoonosis exemplified by the spillover of WNV and Usutu virus (USUV) from the bird-mosquito transmission cycle to humans [11]. Most medically relevant arboviruses belong to the genera *Flavivirus*

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and *Alphavirus* and for most of these viruses no vaccines are available.

Licensed vaccines against yellow fever virus (YFV), Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV), dengue virus (DENV) and Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV) for humans exist. Also for animals licensed vaccines against WNV, JEV and Getah virus exist. The first vaccine that protected from an arbovirus infection was the live-attenuated YFV strain 17D. YFV 17D originates from the Asibi isolate, isolated from an infected individual. This isolate was then passaged in monkeys and mice and finally over 200 times in chicken embryos (Reviewed in [12]). Due to its highly immunogenic character, inducing both innate and adaptive immunity that confer life-long protection, the live-attenuated YFV vaccine is considered one of the most successful human vaccines [13,14]. Although the vaccine is considered very safe, fatal adverse events can occur in immunocompromised individuals. Even though YFV 17D has been used for over 80 years, the molecular mechanisms for its attenuation remain poorly understood [15]. Recent studies found the genetic diversity of YFV 17D to be relatively limited compared to the originally isolated strain, and suggest narrow quasispecies diversity as a plausible correlate of attenuation [16]. The development of live-attenuated vaccines (LAVs) for other arboviruses has raised safety concerns because of the high mutation rate of viral RNA-dependent RNA polymerases [17]. High error rates may lead to mutations that can increase virulence of a vaccine strain, as observed for VEEV TC-83 and multiple CHIKV vaccine candidates [18,19]. Whole virus inactivated vaccines such as the licensed JEV vaccine IXIARO, are considered safer than LAV approaches. However, adjuvants and annual boosters are necessary for long-term protection [20].

The increasing frequency of arbovirus outbreaks and their societal impact stresses the need for reliable platforms that can aid in the rapid development of novel human and animal vaccines, broadly applicable for large groups of arboviruses [21,22]. One such infamous vaccine platform, due to the coronavirus pandemic, is the mRNA platform and variations thereof (e.g. self-amplifying mRNA vaccines). Multiple mRNA vaccine candidates have been developed for various arboviruses, including CHIKV, ZIKV and DENV (reviewed in [23]). Main advantages of mRNA vaccines are the short response time, scalability, reasonable production costs and safety profile. However, vaccine efficacy varies between different mRNA vaccine candidates and multiple boosters for longer duration of immunity are required [24–28]. LAVs, on the other hand, generally elicit a robust immune response with YFV strain 17D as a prime example. Therefore, safe-by-design attenuation strategies that prevent reversion to virulence are of considerable interest. Here we discuss potential approaches for the rational design of novel arbovirus LAVs, recent developments in pan arbovirus vaccine approaches and experimental models that are required for (pre-)clinical evaluations of arbovirus vaccine candidates.

2. Correlates of protection

Arboviruses enter vertebrate hosts when infected mosquitoes inject virus-containing saliva into the dermis during a blood meal. Detection of proteins from the mosquito saliva and viral particles by the host's pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), together with previous immune history and the host's genetic factors determine the nature of the acute, local phase of an arbovirus infection [29–31]. PRRs include membrane-bound Toll-like receptors 3, 7, and 8 [32,33], and cytosolic RIG-I-like receptors (RLRs) [32,34–37], which activate signalling cascades that lead to the induction of type-I interferons (IFN) [38–41]. The type-I IFN response, characterized by cytokine production and expression of IFN stimulated genes (ISGs), establishes a general antiviral state and is critical in controlling arbovirus infections. This is evident from the increased susceptibility of mice lacking the IFN receptor (*Ifnar1*^{-/-}) to arbovirus infections [42–47], compared to the protection offered by pre-treatment with IFN prior to infection [48–51]. There is increasing evidence that the innate response can recollect previous infections via epigenetic reprogramming of innate immune cells to build a *de facto* innate immune

memory called “trained immunity”, which comes into play during subsequent heterogenous and heterologous viral infections [52,53].

IFNs, cytokines and ISGs strengthen adaptive immune responses stimulating the generation of pathogen-specific active (CD4⁺ and CD8⁺) T-cells and B-cells. Both CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T-cells play an important role in antiviral cytokine production and killing of infected cells. IFNs, cytokines and ISGs strengthen adaptive immune responses stimulating the generation of pathogen-specific active (CD4⁺ and CD8⁺) T-cells and B-cells. Both CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T-cells play an important role in antiviral cytokine production and killing of infected cells. Knowledge on the precise immunologic responses to arbovirus antigens is still incomplete and many aspects (e.g. T-cell differentiation into the potential subtypes) are part of active investigations. CD8⁺ memory T-cells play a crucial role in the memory response as effective activation upon flavivirus re-infection generally prevents severe disease including central nervous system pathogenesis in neuroinvasive flavivirus infections [54–61]. During alphavirus infection CD4⁺ T-cells suppress viremia providing protection, while they also play a causative role in alphavirus pathogenesis [62–64]. For example, CHIKV infection or vaccination in mice elicits a CD4⁺ T-cell response which is associated with reduced viremia and increased joint pathology [65,66].

Specialized CD4⁺ T-cells, called follicular helper T (TF_H) cells, support the development of virus-specific B-cell memory responses and the production of high-affinity long-lasting antibodies after viral infections. The main targets for neutralizing antibodies against arboviruses are the envelope proteins (E). For flaviviruses, highly neutralizing antibodies targeting quaternary epitopes of E domain III (EDIII) and residues in the E domain I/II (EDI/EDII) hinge have been identified and isolated from animal models and humans (Fig. 1A) [67–69]. High titers of non-neutralizing antibodies are also produced upon flavivirus infection and generally target the fusion loop of E (FLE), pre-membrane (prM) and non-structural proteins (NS). In some cases there is evidence for neutralization-independent protection associated with these antibodies, e.g. antibody dependent cytotoxicity and antibody dependent complement deposition. Particularly, anti-flavivirus NS1 antibodies protect from infection and severe disease [70–76]. For alphaviruses, most potent neutralizing and protecting antibodies are generated against E1-E2 heterodimer glycoproteins (Fig. 1B). Antibodies against capsid (C) and non-structural proteins (nsP) upon alphavirus infection are also induced [77–79].

Of note, there is a high level of structural and sequence homology between different arbovirus species within the same genus, which can result in cross-reactive B- and T-cell responses [80–84]. For alphaviruses, neutralizing antibodies against conserved epitopes in E2 can provide cross-protection between closely related alphavirus species [85,86]. Moreover, poorly neutralizing antibodies raised against conserved epitopes in E1 were able to protect against more distantly related arthritogenic and encephalitic alphaviruses [87]. While homology between flavivirus EDIII is limited, EDII is highly conserved across the *Flavivirus* genus. Since antibody responses generated against EDII are mainly non-neutralizing, the overall neutralization potential of cross-reactive antibodies is poor [88]. Only early after infection or immunization has antibody cross-protection to heterologous but closely related viruses been observed. For example, cross-protection between DENV and ZIKV infections wanes fast [89]. Moreover, in some cases cross-reactive antibodies can also aid virus entry, resulting in enhanced replication and potentially enhanced disease; a phenomenon termed “antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE)”. ADE has been extensively described for infection of the four different DENV serotypes and is a known feature described in laboratory studies of many pathogenic enveloped viruses of humans and animals [90,91]. Pre-existing DENV immunity is additionally associated with transplacental transmission of ZIKV in experimental models [92,93]. *Vice versa*, ZIKV-specific antibodies may be involved in enhancement of DENV infection [94,95]. Multiple other *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies demonstrated ADE during infection with various other flaviviruses, e.g. YFV, WNV and JEV, as well

A. Flavivirus

B. Alphavirus

Fig. 1. Flavivirus and alphavirus particles. Schematic representation of the spherical flavivirus (A) and alphavirus (B) particles (left). Capsid proteins (C) encapsidate the viral RNA surrounded by a lipid membrane. (A) The surface of the virion contains two proteins, the membrane protein (M) and envelope protein (E). The structure of a West-Nile virus E homodimer is shown (A, right, PDB 7kva). Flavivirus E contains three domains (EDI-III); EDI is highlighted in yellow, EDII in magenta, and EDIII in green. Stem and M-anchor domains are coloured in white. (B) Alphavirus virions contain trimeric spikes of heterodimers that consist of viral envelope proteins E1 and E2 (left). The Chikungunya virus E1-E2 heterodimer structure is displayed (B, right, PDB 3n40). E2 and E1 proteins coloured in dark-red and lila, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

as many other viruses including the alphavirus CHIKV (reviewed in [96,97]). However, clinical and epidemiological data for arbovirus ADE other than DENV is lacking, and thus the clinical significance of these studies remains unknown and requires further investigation.

3. Site-directed attenuation strategies

Introducing specific changes to viral genomes that have been described to attenuate virus replication or reduce pathogenicity can help with the rational design of safer and more efficacious LAVs. However, it is unknown how conserved attenuating mechanisms are across related viruses [98–101]. Furthermore, targeted mutations of conserved amino acids do not necessarily result in similar attenuated phenotypes when applied to different virus species or even to different lineages of the same virus [102,103]. However, some promising mechanisms have not only shown consistent attenuation across different viral species within a genus, but were also found to be applicable to both flaviviruses and alphaviruses (Fig. 2 and Table 1).

A promising strategy to attenuate flavivirus and alphavirus entry are targeted mutations in the envelope (E) proteins that enhance glycosaminoglycan (GAG) affinity. GAGs are hydrophilic polysaccharides found in mammalian connective tissues, on cell surfaces and the extracellular matrix, which can act as receptors for a number of viruses. In animal models, multiple flaviviruses and alphaviruses with increased GAG affinity were found to be sequestered in the extracellular matrix and in GAG-rich organs. This resulted in reduced neuroinvasiveness and increased the rate of viral clearance from the blood, which subsequently led to improved survival rates (Table 1) [99,101,104–109]. Furthermore, pre-exposure to an attenuated CHIKV GAG-mutant protected mice upon a subsequent challenge with wild-type virus [110]. Moreover,

increased GAG affinity is also considered to be the mode of action for one of the mutations associated with the attenuation of the life-attenuated JEV SA14–14-2 vaccine [111]. However, GAG binding has also been observed to promote infection in specific tissues which highlights the complexity of manipulating viral pathology through GAG-associated mutations alone [107,112]. In addition to GAG affinity, mutations located in the fusion domain of the JEV SA14–14-2 E protein attenuated virus replication [113]. This fusion site is highly conserved among flaviviruses, and introducing a homologous mutation in WNV also resulted in attenuation in mice (Table 1) [114].

Other promising targets are N-glycosylation sites. N-glycosylation sites are highly conserved motifs which are present in both flaviviruses and alphaviruses. N-linked glycosylation is the most common post-translational modification of proteins and it can affect a plethora of processes including protein folding, transport and receptor binding. N-glycosylation of viral proteins can therefore affect virus infectivity for example by modulating virus replication, assembly, attachment and cell entry [115–117]. Targeted removal of N-glycosylation sites in either the PrM [116], E or NS1 protein of flaviviruses (reviewed in [117]), or the E1 domain of the alphavirus E protein [118,119], consistently resulted in attenuation in animal models (Table 1). Furthermore, mice pre-exposed to JEV and WNV bearing N-glycosylation site mutations in the E protein were protected upon subsequent challenge with corresponding wild-type viruses [120,121].

In addition to mutations in structural proteins, specific amino acid residues in nonstructural proteins that are involved in innate immune evasion, such as NS5 in flaviviruses, and a conserved proline in nsP2 of alphaviruses are appealing targets for virus attenuation. Mutations in both proteins have shown to attenuate virulence in animal models (Table 1) [122–124]. Furthermore, mutations in the flavivirus non-

A. Flavivirus

B. Alphavirus

★ N-Glycosylation Site

Fig. 2. Flavivirus and alphavirus genome organization and indicated targets for attenuation. (A) Schematic representation of the flavivirus single-stranded RNA genome. The 10–11 kb genome is flanked by a capped 5'UTR and a highly-structured 3' untranslated region responsible for the formation of subgenomic-flavivirus RNA (sfRNA). The single open-reading frame codes for one poly-protein which is cleaved into three structural (C, prM, and E) and five non-structural proteins (NS). (B) The alphavirus single-stranded RNA genome of 11–12 kb is capped and polyadenylated, and contains two open-reading frames. The first and second open-reading frame code for four non-structural (nsPs), and structural proteins (C, E1, E2, and E3), respectively. Sites for targeted, attenuating mutations are indicated in the flavivirus and alphavirus genome.

coding regions e.g. subgenomic flavivirus RNA (sfRNA) attenuate DENV and WNV replication *in vitro* and WNV *in vivo* in vertebrates [125–129] and mosquitoes [130–134]. Establishing whether such mutations could be used more broadly will require more comprehensive research [98,99]. An alternative strategy is disrupting replication fidelity of a virus. Although YFV 17D was shown to have increased replication fidelity, it remains to be shown that either increasing or decreasing the fidelity can result in reliable attenuated vaccine candidates [19,135].

It is clear however that multiple mutations contribute to attenuation of JEV SA14–14-2, as well YFV 17D, and this is an important note for rationally designed LAVs in order to minimize the risk of reversion to virulence. Incorporating multiple attenuating mutations and carefully assessing the stability of the designed changes as well as whether compensating mutations evolve will be important for evaluating the safety of any vaccine candidate [136,137].

4. Chimeric virus vaccines

Instead of introducing attenuating mutations, the narrow quasispecies diversity and genomic stability of YFV 17D offers opportunities for the use of the YFV 17D genetic backbone for the development of vaccines by chimerization [163]. ChimeriVax (Sanofi Pasteur) is a vaccine platform designed to swap the structural prM and E proteins of YFV 17D for heterologous flavivirus prME resulting in recombinant LAVs with the expected safety profile of YFV 17D (Fig. 2). Numerous YFV 17D chimeric vaccine candidates have been developed using the ChimeriVax technology including Dengvaxia (DENV1, DENV2, DENV3, and DENV4), IMOJEV (JEV), ChimeriVax-Zika (CYZ; ZIKV) [164] and ChimeriVax-

WN02 (WNV) (reviewed in [165]). For all four candidates, low levels of viremia and high titers of neutralizing antibodies were observed in human clinical trials [164–167]. Furthermore, chimeric YFV 17D with ZIKV prM and E was found to protect mice from a lethal challenge of not only ZIKV, but also YFV in mouse model systems [168]. IMOJEV and Dengvaxia are now licenced for human use in Australia and DENV endemic countries, respectively. However, for Dengvaxia low vaccine efficacy against some serotypes and ADE resulting in severe dengue disease was observed in vaccinated seronegative individuals [169,170]. This prominent safety concern mandates serological pre-screening of vaccinees which limits vaccine efficacy and applicability of Dengvaxia, especially in resource-poor settings. Next to Dengvaxia, two other DENV tetravalent chimeric vaccine candidates are currently in development. Takeda's tetravalent chimeric DENV vaccine candidate (TAK-003) is constructed using the backbone of the attenuated DENV serotype-2 PDK-53 with inserted the prM and E genes of the other three DENV serotypes [171]. Unlike Dengvaxia, TAK-003 has shown to be efficacious and safe for use in both seronegative and seropositive participants and is now approved in Brazil [172–175]. The attenuated DENV-2 PDK-53 has also been successfully used to develop chimeric vaccine candidates for ZIKV and WNV that protected animals against a subsequent lethal challenge with ZIKV and WNV [176,177]. Butantan-DV tetravalent vaccine candidate (TV-003/005) is formulated as a mixture of DENV1, DENV3, and DENV4 with a 30 nucleotide deletion in their 3'UTR (DENV1/3/4-Δ30), and chimeric DEN2/4Δ30 with DENV2 prM and E genes inserted in the attenuated DENV4Δ30 backbone [178]. In a clinical phase II trial, vaccination with Butantan-DV was safe and well tolerated, and showed the induction of a well-balanced B-cell and T-cell response against all

Table 1
Summary of conserved attenuating mutations across multiple A) flaviviruses and B) alphaviruses.

Target	Outcome Summary	Viruses	Model Used	Ref.
A) Flaviviruses:				
PrM Glycosylation	Removal of the PrM glycosylation site attenuates neuroinvasion and neurovirulence in mice (JEV) and inhibits viral release and spread <i>in vitro</i> (ZIKV).	JEV	ICR mice (i.p/i.c)	[138]
		ZIKV	<i>In vitro</i> : Vero Cells	[116]
Env Glycosylation	Removal of the envelope glycosylation site consistently results in increased survival and reduced viral loads in peripheral infection (i.p or s.c). Reduction in neurovirulence was shown for JEV and WNV, as well as survival against a WT virus challenge.	JEV	C57BL/6 mice (i.p/i.c)	[120]
		WNV	Swiss mice (i.p/i.c)	[114,121]
		ZIKV	A129 mice (s.c/i.c)	[139]
		MVEV	Swiss mice (i.p)	[140]
		TBEV	C57BL/6 mice (s.c)	[141]
		TMUV	Cherry Valley ducks (i.c)	[142]
		JEV	Swiss Outbred mice (i.v, i.c, i.p)	[144]
GAG binding affinity	Incorporating positive charge amino acids into the envelope which enhance affinity for GAG receptors results in increased survival and reduced viral loads from peripheral infection (i.p or s.c), and an increased rate of viral clearance from blood (i.v). TBEV results also show survival against a WT virus challenge. Neurovirulence (i.c) however is either maintained or increased.	WNV	IFN- α/γ -R-/- mice (i.v, s.c)	[143]
		DENV	Swiss Outbred mice (i.p, i.c), BALB/c mice (i.v,)	[145]
		MVEV	Swiss Outbred mice (i.v,)	[146]
		TBEV	IFN- α/γ -R-/- mice (i.p, i.v, i.c)	[147]
		TMUV	Swiss Outbred mice (i.p, i.c)	[149]
		JEV	Swiss Outbred (s.c), ICR mice (s.c, i.c)	[148]
		WNV	Pekin ducklings (i.c, s.c)	[149]
		JEV	ICR mice (i.c)	[150]
		WNV	ICR mice & NIH Swiss mice (i.p, i.c)	[114]
		NS1 Glycosylation	Removal of one or more glycosylation sites results in an attenuated phenotype, but there is variation in which specific sites and whether a peripheral or a neurovirulence model was used.	YFV
DENV	ICR mice (i.c)			[152]
WNV	NIH Swiss mice (i.c, i.p)			[153]
TMUV	Ducklings (i.m)			[149]
NS5 Methyl-transferase sfRNA	Disrupting the active site results in attenuation in a peripheral infection model, as well as survival against a WT virus challenge. Mutations and deletions that disrupt sfRNA attenuate WNV, ZIKV and DENV.	JEV	BALB/c mice (i.p, i.c)	[154]
		WNV	C3H mice (s.c, i.p)	[123]
		WNV	Swiss outbred mice (i.p.)	[125,155,156]
		DENV		
B) Alphaviruses:				
Env Glycosylation	Removal of the E1 site is attenuating, but the E2 site had little effect. Removal of the E1 site was less virulent but removal of the E2 site enhanced neurovirulence.	RRV	C57BL/6 mice (s.c)	[121]
		SINV	CD-1 mice, C57BL/6 mice (i.c)	[122]
GAG binding affinity	Incorporating positive charge amino acids into the envelope which enhance affinity for GAG receptors results in increased survival and reduced viral loads from peripheral infection (i.p, s.c) and increased rate of viral clearance from blood (i.v). Neurovirulence (i.c) however is either maintained or increased.	CHIKV	CD-1 mice, STAT129 mice (s.c)	[157]
		SFV	BALB/c mice (i.p, i.c)	[158]
		SINV	Neonatal ICR-L+ mice (s.c)	[159]
		VEEV	CD-1 mice (s.c, i.v)	[109]
		EEEEV*	CD-1 mice (s.c, i.c)	[112]
nsP2 IFN Signalling	Mutations of conserved proline disrupts nsP2 function in vitro (CHIKV) and attenuates virulence in mice (SINV).	SINV	Suckling mice (i.c)	[122]
		CHIKV	<i>In vitro</i> : Vero Cells	[124]
nsP3 Opal Site	Conflicting results (whether removing or adding a stop codon is attenuating is virus dependent).	SFV SINV	BALB/c AnNHsd mice (i.p)	[160]
		CHIKV	CD-1 mice (i.c)	[161]
			C57BL/6 J (s.c)	[162]

* Study looked at removal of positive charge amino acid in naturally neurovirulent strain. Intraperitoneal (i.p), Subcutaneous (s.c), Intracranial (i.c), intravenous (i.v),

four DENV serotypes [179]. The induction of a balanced immune response is desirable as it is believed that next to the quality, the quantity of pre-existing antibodies can modulate the host's immune response upon a subsequent challenge or vaccination (reviewed in [180]). The live-attenuated JEV SA14-14-2 has been used as a backbone to develop a ZIKV chimeric vaccine candidate (ChinZIKV). ChinZIKV induces strong and long-lasting immunity and fully protected adult mice and fetus, as well as rhesus macaques against ZIKV challenge [181]. To create alphavirus chimeric vaccines, a relatively non-pathogenic virus like Sindbis virus (SINV) or an attenuated virus strain like VEEV TC-83 or Eastern equine encephalitis (EEEEV) BeAr436087 has been used to exchange E1/E2 proteins (Fig. 2). The chimeric vaccine candidates SINV/CHIKV, VEEV/CHIKV, and EEEV /CHIKV showed attenuation, induced high levels of neutralizing antibodies and protected mice upon lethal challenges with CHIKV [182–184]. Also WEEV/EEEEV chimera were attenuated and protected mice against a lethal challenge with EEEV [185].

Another promising strategy for making chimeric vaccines is using insect-specific relatives of flaviviruses and alphaviruses. Even though phylogenetic studies indicate that insect-specific viruses (ISVs) are related to vertebrate infecting viruses, empirical studies provide experimental evidence that they are restricted to replication in insects [186–189]. This allows for the design of safe chimeric vaccines using the genetic backbone of ISVs with the structural cassette of pathogenic arboviruses. The insect-specific alphavirus Eilat virus (EILV) was the first ISV used to create a chimeric vaccine candidate with CHIKV. The EILV/CHIKV chimeric virion is structurally identical to wild-type CHIKV and able to enter and deliver its viral RNA in vertebrate cells. However, the chimeric RNA is replication incompetent both *in vitro* and *in vivo* in vertebrates. Using EILV/CHIKV for vaccination showed high and robust levels of immunogenicity and protected mice from subsequent CHIKV infection [190]. Similarly, the insect-specific flavivirus Binjari virus (BinJV) was used to create BinJV/ZIKV, BinJV/WNV, BinJV/DENV-2, and BinJV/YFV chimera for vaccination purposes [191–193]. BinJV

chimera were able to enter vertebrate cells, yet failed to produce progeny virus, and showed high levels of protective immunity in mouse models. ISV/arbovirus chimera are still able to grow to high titers in mosquito cells, which can be exploited for the production of these ISV/arbovirus chimeric vaccines.

5. Recoded virus vaccines

Eighteen of the twenty amino acids are encoded by more than one codon. This redundancy in the genetic code leaves room for selective use of nucleotides and codons without changing the encoded protein through synonymous mutations. Multiples of such synonymous mutations can be used to recode viral genomes and specifically alter the nucleotide, dinucleotide and codon (pair) usage frequencies. While this strategy results in “silent” changes to the protein product, synonymous recoding can affect the fate of the RNA with potential effects on RNA turnover, translation efficacy, RNA replication, and engagement with cellular factors that recognize certain RNA patterns (reviewed in [194]). This provides opportunities for the design and engineering of LAVs as the viral genome can be intentionally deoptimized for replication in a

host by means of synonymous changes (Fig. 3A).

Most viruses display codon usage frequencies that reflect the genome composition of the host. This mimicry is reasonable because a virus uses the host's machinery for the translation of viral proteins, resulting in the optimal use of the host's available tRNAs to recognize the viral codons. Moreover, certain codon pairs are used more frequently, and other pairs are avoided; this is known as codon pair bias. A ribosome decodes codon pairs during translation; thus, codon pair bias alters the translation elongation rate and may alter protein folding and the coordinated expression of functionally grouped proteins [195–197]. Large-scale genomic synonymous recoding such as random codon shuffling, codon-deoptimization, and codon-pair deoptimization all resulted in attenuated replication of CHIKV, DENV, TBEV, and ZIKV in vertebrate and invertebrate cells [198–202]. In addition, synonymously changing codons to be one mutation away from becoming a stop codon decreased the mutational robustness of CHIKV and attenuated virus replication *in vitro* and *in vivo* in mice and mosquitoes [203]. Furthermore, randomly recoded TBEV and codon-pair deoptimized ZIKV showed an attenuated phenotype *in vivo* and protected mice upon subsequent lethal challenges with wild-type virus, and blocked the vertical transmission of ZIKV

Fig. 3. Codon and dinucleotide usage in flaviviruses and alphaviruses. (A) Viral genomes can be recoded with synonymous changes that affect the codon usage, codon-pair usage and/or dinucleotide frequencies. (B) Data points represent observed/expected (O/E) CpG (x-axis) and UpA (y-axis) dinucleotide-frequencies, with the expected frequencies calculated from a random distribution of the RNA's mononucleotides. Data points represent full length genomes of distinct vertebrate-infecting flavivirus species (blue) and alphavirus species (orange). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

during pregnancy [200,204]. However, changing the distribution of codons and codon-pairs correspondingly alters the (di)nucleotide usage and recent studies suggest that the avoidance of CpG and UpA is a main driver for the observed codon distribution in viral genomes (Fig. 3A) [205–209].

The suppression of CpG and UpA dinucleotides in viral genomes mirrors the underrepresentation of these dinucleotides in the RNA of humans and other vertebrate animals. Many vertebrate RNA viruses including flaviviruses have evolved to suppress their CpG and UpA dinucleotides (Fig. 3B) [210,211]. The intentional introduction of hundreds of CpG and/or UpA dinucleotides by synonymous recoding attenuates the replication of diverse vertebrate viruses including ZIKV and protected mice upon subsequent challenge with wild-type ZIKV [212,213]. In vertebrate cells, sequences rich in CpG dinucleotides are recognized by the vertebrate zinc-finger antiviral protein (ZAP). ZAP is connected with the IFN response, stimulates RNA degradation and inhibits translation initiation [214–220]. Knockout of ZAP rescues the attenuated phenotype of CpG-high virus mutants and in some studies also improve replication of attenuated UpA-high virus [212,216]. However, in what way ZAP is involved in the attenuation of UpA-high virus mutants is unclear [221].

In contrast to vertebrates, mosquito RNA contains unbiased frequencies of CpG dinucleotides. Interestingly, CpG-high ZIKV mutants that were attenuated in vertebrate cells displayed enhanced replication rates in mosquito cells and improved virus dissemination to the salivary glands in live mosquitoes compared to wild-type ZIKV [212]. This strongly suggests that deoptimizing arboviruses for replication in vertebrate cells can improve virus replication in mosquito cells. Compared to flaviviruses, alphaviruses have evolved higher CpG dinucleotide frequencies in their genomes, which is more similar to the unbiased frequencies in mosquito RNA (Fig. 3B). Wild-type alphaviruses are highly sensitive to overexpression of vertebrate ZAP [222]. However, it remains to be tested whether further elevating CpG dinucleotides in alphaviruses attenuates replication in the vertebrate host.

Synonymously recoded, attenuated viruses have protein structures that are identical to wild-type viruses and are therefore expected to induce a specific and strong immune response. Attenuation by recoding involves the introduction of hundreds nucleotide substitutions that all contribute to the attenuated phenotype, thereby greatly reducing the risk of reversion to wild-type virulence [198]. Elevating levels of CpG and UpA dinucleotides has the potential to attenuate mosquito-borne viruses as well as many vertebrate-specific viruses (reviewed in [194]). Elucidating underlying molecular mechanisms of attenuation provides a rationale for the safe use of CpG-high mutant viruses and opportunities to grow attenuated viruses in specific knockout cells. Moreover, CpG-high LAVs can also grow to high titers in mosquito cells. However, there is little data available on the safety and efficacy of this approach. It will therefore be imperative to investigate the level of attenuation and potential infection of specific tissues (e.g. central nervous system, placenta). With the observed enhanced replication in mosquitoes, also the potential for vaccine transmission and persistent infections in mosquito populations need to be taken into account during vaccine development.

6. Mosquito saliva-based vaccine

While taking a bloodmeal, mosquitoes inject saliva into the host's skin [223,224], inoculating a mixture of several dozen proteins and other bioactive molecules that can affect local virus accumulation and further virus dissemination [225]. Importantly, the presence of mosquito saliva at the bite site skews the local immune balance towards a T-helper (Th) 2 response, which is inferior in restricting virus growth compared to Th1-biased responses [31,226–228]. This increases viral load in the skin and in the blood, and accelerated mortality of the host [29,170,225,229–232].

Considering its virus-enhancing properties, mosquito saliva has

emerged as a novel target to impede mosquito-borne virus infections. The concept relies on immunization of individuals with crude mosquito saliva or selected, usually immunomodulatory, saliva proteins to prime an immune response against those components. After an infectious mosquito bite, inhibition of bioactive saliva components should prevent skewing of Th1 to Th2 responses resulting in a more favorable Th1-dominated immune response. Indeed, immunizing mice with a high dose of whole salivary gland homogenate from *Culex tarsalis* increased the production of Th1-type cytokines and, after a mosquito-transmitted WNV challenge, resulted in reduced mortality and less virus dissemination to the brain [233]. Similarly, immunization of mice with *Aedes aegypti* salivary proteins AgBR1 [234,235], NeST1 [236], or a combination of those [237] protected against ZIKV disease after an infectious mosquito bite. While immunization with these immunomodulatory proteins was able to protect against disease in mouse models, vaccine strategies using other saliva components (or cocktails hereof) have resulted in enhanced virus replication or aggravated disease [238,239]. These salivary proteins are unsuitable for vaccine development and caution must be taken when creating a vaccine based on individual mosquito salivary proteins.

While some promising proof-of-principle studies for saliva-based vaccine candidates have been reported for pathogens transmitted by sandflies and ticks [240–244], the clinical development of a mosquito saliva-based vaccine is still in its infancy. In a recent phase 1 clinical trial, a single-dose vaccine based on recombinant *Anopheles gambiae* salivary proteins was tested for its safety and immunogenicity in humans [245]. In this study, no safety concerns were identified, while saliva-specific antibody responses and the production of Th1-type cytokines were triggered. Of note, this response was partly dependent on the addition of an adjuvant to the saliva-based vaccine, thus a fraction of the induced immune response was stimulated by the adjuvant rather than the mosquito salivary proteins [246]. The saliva-specific antibodies were maintained for at least 3 months but diminished after 1 year [245]. To date, this is the only study that has evaluated the effect of a mosquito saliva-based vaccine in humans, and although it provides data regarding the immunogenicity of such a vaccine, no pathogen exposure was conducted. Whether it provides humans with protection against pathogens transmitted by *Anopheles gambiae* thus remains to be determined.

Besides the longevity of immune responses, the development of saliva-based vaccines faces additional challenges that need to be addressed: For locals, long-term exposure to mosquito allergens may lead to desensitization, apparent by waning immediate and delayed immune responses to mosquito saliva [247]. This could make a saliva-based vaccine more relevant for naïve travellers who plan short-term visits to endemic areas. Moreover, in a longitudinal study, children with higher antibody levels against *Aedes aegypti* salivary proteins were 1.5 times more likely to develop inapparent DENV infection, challenging the idea of a monovalent saliva-based vaccine strategy [248]. Instead, immunization with salivary proteins could be moved forward as an adjuvant for pathogen-targeted vaccines, a concept that has been tested for sandfly saliva and *Leishmaniasis* infection in mice [249]. In conclusion, while saliva-based vaccines have emerged as new strategy with the potential to affect replication of multiple viruses transmitted by the same mosquito species, many practical hurdles still need to be taken into account, in particular the identification and validation of effective vaccine targets within the complex blend of mosquito saliva proteins.

7. In vitro models

Thorough safety assessment of candidate LAVs must be carried out to ensure that pathogenesis and transmission have been sufficiently attenuated, whilst maintaining immunogenicity. As many arboviruses are able to cause severe neurological disease in a subset of infected individuals, *in vitro* models of neuroinvasion and neuropathogenesis can be used to gain insight into the attenuation of these key stages of disease progression.

Such models range in complexity from 2D cell line monocultures to 3D organ/vessel on a chip and *ex vivo* organoids [250,251]. Due to the broad cell tropism of many arboviruses, 2D and 3D co-culture models with relevant neuronal and neurovascular cell types would provide the most complete picture into the degree of attenuation of neuroinvasion and pathogenesis of vaccine candidates. To model the effect of attenuation on virus transmission, *in vitro* and *ex vivo* human skin models and mosquito cell lines can provide a rapid initial indication, but this complex phenotype eventually requires validation in *in vivo* transmission models [252].

To predict immunogenicity and antigenicity of vaccine candidates, *in silico* techniques can be applied [251,253]. This can streamline the vaccine candidate selection process prior to *in vitro* assessment of immunogenicity using primary human, or human derived immune cells to identify cytokine responses and induction of cell maturation and proliferation [253]. For some viruses the route of vaccination may influence the subsequent immune response [254,255], so more complex 3D models that recapitulate features of the human immune system within relevant physiological contexts, such as skin, could also be employed to refine assessment of immunogenicity and act as a bridge to successive *in vivo* studies.

Indeed, whilst *in silico* and *in vitro* models are essential tools in the development and selection of safe and effective arboviral vaccine candidates, the data obtained cannot be fully extrapolated to the physiological setting. Further, characteristics such as the viraemic profile and transmissibility of LAV candidates cannot be obtained *in vitro*.

8. *In vivo* models to assess vaccine safety and efficacy

Assessing vaccine efficacy *in vivo* requires challenging vaccinated animals with virus. This is generally done via needle-inoculation, typically via the intraperitoneal route. Importantly, needle-delivery of arboviruses does not model important parameters of the natural infection, such as immunomodulatory factors of mosquito saliva that are co-inoculated into the bite site during virus transmission [224]. These salivary factors play a key role in the establishment and potentiation of virus infection in the vertebrate host [31,226–228]. When hamsters were vaccinated against VEEV they were fully protected from both needle- and infectious mosquito-challenge [256]. Likewise, challenging mice [257], cats and dogs [258], or horses [257,259] via an infectious mosquito bite subsequent to WNV vaccination resulted in protection against WNV disease and no development of detectable viremia. However, comparing needle-inoculation with mosquito-delivery of arboviruses in animal models shows differential immune responses [227], viremia [260–263], disease progression [225,262], and tissue tropism [261]. These aspects should be taken into account when assessing vaccine efficacy and safety *in vivo*, considering arboviruses and other arthropod-borne pathogens can become more virulent when inoculated via a mosquito bite [29]. For example, when *Plasmodium*-vaccinated mice were challenged with *Plasmodium* sporozoite infection, the needle-challenged mice were fully protected whereas protection was significantly limited for mice challenged via a mosquito bite [264]. Comparably, vaccination against *Leishmania* protected mice against subsequent needle-challenge with *Leishmania*, but this protection was completely abolished when mice were challenged via infected sandfly exposure [265]. These findings highlight the fact that conventional *in vivo* challenge models cannot be readily extrapolated to the natural setting. Even so, vaccination studies employing a mosquito-challenge mouse model to predict the protective efficacy of arbovirus vaccines in humans are not typically implemented.

For *in vivo* testing of vaccine candidates, employing (i) infectious mosquito biting, (ii) non-infectious mosquito probing prior to challenge, or (iii) co-inoculation of virus with mosquito saliva or salivary gland extract as standard for challenge may aid in predicting vaccination efficacy against natural exposure to infectious mosquitoes. Furthermore, *in vivo* models can aid in testing the likelihood of LAVs to be taken up

from an inoculated animal by vector mosquitoes and thus the transmission potential of LAVs.

9. Future perspectives

Classical LAVs, like YFV 17D, have been shown to be more successful in disease prevention than their inactivated counterparts. LAVs are similar to natural infection in their antigen load and presentation to the immune system. Therefore, LAVs are strong inducers of the innate and adaptive response resulting in generation of strain specific T-cells and neutralizing antibodies that confer (life-long) protection. Classical LAVs (e.g. YFV 17D, vaccinia against smallpox, measles/mumps/rubella vaccine, oral poliovirus vaccine) have been safely used in humans for decades. Nevertheless, attenuation by repeated passage is the result of random mutations [266], and poses several risks (e.g. reversion to wild-type and pathogenicity in immunocompromised individuals) that limit the development of new LAVs [267]. Therefore, novel approaches need to be safe-by-design and provide the desired level of attenuation and sufficient stability of the attenuating mutations. Combining multiple mutations in conserved functional sites, generating chimeras with established, attenuated viral backbones or genome-wide recoding are promising strategies to design novel LAV candidates. These attenuating strategies can also be combined to further reduce replication and/or pathogenicity, e.g. mutations in specific neurotropic-related residues in the E protein of YFV/WNV and YFV/JEV chimeras [113,268]. In addition to creating novel LAVs, mosquito salivary proteins may be utilized as pan arbovirus vaccines or adjuvants to enhance protection against arbovirus disease.

Preclinical evaluation of novel arbovirus LAV candidates requires relevant *in vitro* and *in vivo* model systems to assess pathogenicity in different tissues and the quality of immune responses that are induced. Moreover, a natural viral infection via mosquito bite can change the outcome of infection compared to challenge by needle injection. It is therefore crucial that novel mosquito-borne virus vaccines are also evaluated in the context of a natural transmission route. Direct comparisons of novel LAVs with established vaccines such as YFV 17D may provide valuable information on e.g. the functionality, breadth and longevity of elicited T and B-cell responses. It is important to note that although we discuss broadly applicable vaccination strategies, there are substantial differences in tissue tropism, pathogenicity and outcome of disease between viral species that need to be taken into account during (pre-)clinical evaluations. The prime example is ADE of dengue virus infections. The tetravalent chimeric vaccine Dengvaxia, successfully passed all (pre-)clinical evaluations and vaccination resulted in high and robust levels of neutralizing antibodies. However, upon implementation, ADE resulting in severe dengue disease was observed in vaccinated seronegative individuals [169,170]. Although there is currently no clinical and epidemiological data that describes ADE of other arbovirus infections, experimental evidence from multiple arbovirus species warrants the careful consideration of potential negative immune interactions between different arboviruses [95,96].

The combination of broadly applicable vaccination strategies and relevant *in vitro* and *in vivo* model systems to assess vaccine safety and efficacy will aid in the rapid development of novel arbovirus vaccines. Particularly, mosquito transmission and challenge experiments can provide additional data on the efficacy of vaccines against natural infections. Together, the topics discussed can provide promising strategies to target the direct interface of the vertebrate host, the mosquito vector and the viral pathogen, with potential to alleviate arbovirus disease burden in human and animal populations.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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References

- [1] L. Reperant, A.O. Vaccine, undefined. *AIDS, Avian flu, SARS, MERS, Ebola, Zika what next?* Elsevier, 2017.
- [2] A.T. Ciota, A.C. Keyel, The role of temperature in transmission of zoonotic arboviruses, *Viruses* 11 (2019).
- [3] A.T. Ciota, et al., Differential effects of temperature and mosquito genetics determine transmissibility of arboviruses by *Aedes aegypti* in Argentina, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 99 (2018) 417–424.
- [4] T.C. Pierson, M.S. Diamond, The continued threat of emerging flaviviruses, *Nat. Microbiol.* 5 (2020) 796–812.
- [5] J.J. Fros, et al., West Nile Virus: high transmission rate in north-western European mosquitoes indicates its epidemic potential and warrants increased surveillance, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 9 (2015), e0003956.
- [6] E. Muttis, et al., Factors related to *Aedes aegypti* (Diptera: Culicidae) populations and temperature determine differences on life-history traits with regional implications in disease transmission, *J. Med. Entomol.* 55 (2018) 1105–1112.
- [7] J.J. Fros, et al., Comparative Usutu and West Nile virus transmission potential by local *Culex pipiens* mosquitoes in north-western Europe, *One Heal.* 1 (2015) 31–36.
- [8] Y.J.S. Huang, S. Higgs, D.L. Vanlandingham, Emergence and re-emergence of mosquito-borne arboviruses, *Curr. Opin. Virol.* 34 (2019) 104–109.
- [9] L.M. Hernández-Triana, et al., Emergence of West Nile virus lineage 2 in Europe: A review on the introduction and spread of a mosquito-borne disease, *Front. Public Health* 2 (2014) 271.
- [10] M.S. Cunha, et al., Chikungunya virus: an emergent arbovirus to the south American continent and a continuous threat to the world, *Front. Microbiol.* 11 (2020) 1297.
- [11] M. Pfeffer, G. Dobler, Emergence of zoonotic arboviruses by animal trade and migration, *Parasit. Vectors* 3 (2010) 35.
- [12] J.G. Frierson, The yellow fever vaccine: a history, *Yale J. Biol. Med.* 83 (2010) 77.
- [13] J. Lang, et al., Comparison of the immunogenicity and safety of two 17D yellow fever vaccines, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 60 (1999) 1045–1050.
- [14] L. Antonio Bastos Camacho, et al., Immunogenicity of WHO-17D and Brazilian 17DD yellow fever vaccines: a randomized trial, *SciELO Bras.* 38 (2004) 671–679.
- [15] N.D. Collins, A.D.T. Barrett, Live attenuated yellow fever 17D vaccine: a legacy vaccine still controlling outbreaks in modern day, *Curr. Infect. Dis. Rep.* 19 (2017).
- [16] A. Beck, et al., Comparison of the live attenuated yellow fever vaccine 17D-204 strain to its virulent parental strain Asibi by deep sequencing, *J. Infect. Dis.* 209 (2014) 334–344.
- [17] J.W. Drake, J.J. Holland, Mutation rates among RNA viruses, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 96 (1999) 13910–13913.
- [18] I. Tretyakova, et al., Novel DNA-launched Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus vaccine with rearranged genome, *Vaccine* 37 (2019) 3317–3325.
- [19] C.M. Weiss, H. Liu, K.K. Riemersma, E.E. Ball, L.L. Coffey, Engineering a fidelity-variant live-attenuated vaccine for chikungunya virus, *npj Vaccin.* 51 (5) (2020) 1–13.
- [20] S.T. Duggan, G.L. Plosker, Japanese encephalitis vaccine (inactivated, adsorbed) [IXIARO], *Drugs* 69 (2009) 115–122.
- [21] L.A. Reperant, A.D.M.E. Osterhaus, AIDS, Avian flu, SARS, MERS, Ebola, Zika... what next? *Vaccine* 35 (2017) 4470–4474.
- [22] D. R., S. R., R. S. & J. F., Climatic effects on mosquito abundance in Mediterranean wetlands, *Parasit. Vectors* 7 (2014).
- [23] C.J. Wollner, J.M. Richner, mRNA Vaccines against Flaviviruses, *Vaccines* 9 (2021) 148.
- [24] A. Cagigi, K. Loré, Immune Responses Induced by mRNA Vaccination in Mice, Monkeys and Humans, *Vaccines* 9 (2021) 1–14.
- [25] J. Chen, J. Chen, Q. Xu, Current developments and challenges of mRNA vaccines. *doi:10.1146/annurev-bioeng-110220-031722* 24, 2022, pp. 85–109.
- [26] B. Essink, et al., The safety and immunogenicity of two Zika virus mRNA vaccine candidates in healthy flavivirus baseline seropositive and seronegative adults: the results of two randomised, placebo-controlled, dose-ranging, phase 1 clinical trials, *Lancet Infect. Dis.* (2023), [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(22\)00764-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(22)00764-2).
- [27] N. Ge, et al., An mRNA vaccine encoding Chikungunya virus E2-E1 protein elicits robust neutralizing antibody responses and CTL immune responses, *Virol. Sin.* 37 (2022) 266–276.
- [28] Z. Zhong, et al., Immunogenicity and protection efficacy of a naked self-replicating mRNA-based Zika virus vaccine, *Vaccines* 7 (2019) 96.
- [29] M. Pingen, et al., Host Inflammatory Response to Mosquito Bites Enhances the Severity of Arbovirus Infection, *Immunity* 44 (2016) 1455–1469.
- [30] M. Pingen, M.A. Schmid, E. Harris, C.S. McKimmie, Mosquito Biting Modulates Skin Response to Virus Infection, *Trends Parasitol.* 33 (2017) 645–657.
- [31] B.S. Schneider, S. Higgs, The enhancement of arbovirus transmission and disease by mosquito saliva is associated with modulation of the host immune response, *Trans. R. Soc. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 102 (2008) 400–408.
- [32] A.M.A. Nasirudeen, et al., RIG-I, MDA5 and TLR3 synergistically play an important role in restriction of dengue virus infection, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 5 (2011).
- [33] Z. Her, et al., Loss of TLR3 aggravates CHIKV replication and pathology due to an altered virus-specific neutralizing antibody response, *EMBO Mol. Med.* 7 (2015) 24.
- [34] D. Olagnier, et al., Inhibition of dengue and chikungunya virus infections by RIG-I-mediated type I interferon-independent stimulation of the innate antiviral response, *J. Virol.* 88 (2014) 4180–4194.
- [35] Y.M. Loo, M. Gale, Immune signaling by RIG-I-like receptors, *Immunity* 34 (2011) 680–692.
- [36] B.L. Fredericksen, B.C. Keller, J. Fornek, M.G. Katze, M. Gale, Establishment and maintenance of the innate antiviral response to west Nile virus involves both RIG-I and MDA5 signaling through IPS-1, *J. Virol.* 82 (2008) 609–616.
- [37] J.W. Schoggins, et al., A diverse range of gene products are effectors of the type I interferon antiviral response, *Nature* 472 (2011) 481–485.
- [38] S. Goodbourn, L. Didcock, R.E. Randall, Interferons: Cell signalling, immune modulation, antiviral responses and virus countermeasures, *J. Gen. Virol.* 81 (2000) 2341–2364.
- [39] M.S. Diamond, B. Shrestha, E. Mehlhop, E. Sitati, M. Engle, Innate and adaptive immune responses determine protection against disseminated infection by west Nile encephalitis, *Virus*. <https://home.liebertpub.com/vim> 16 (2004) 259–278.
- [40] L.-J. Ho, et al., Infection of human dendritic cells by dengue virus causes cell maturation and cytokine production, *J. Immunol.* 166 (2001) 1499–1506.
- [41] L.J. Johnston, G.M. Halliday, N.J. King, Phenotypic changes in Langerhans' cells after infection with arboviruses: a role in the immune response to epidermally acquired viral infection? *J. Virol.* 70 (1996) 4761–4766.
- [42] R. Lindqvist, et al., Fast type I interferon response protects astrocytes from flavivirus infection and virus-induced cytopathic effects, *J. Neuroinflammation* 13 (2016) 1–15.
- [43] S.Y. Hwang, et al., A null mutation in the gene encoding a type I interferon receptor component eliminates antiproliferative and antiviral responses to interferons alpha and beta and alters, *Natl. Acad. Sci.* 92 (1995) 11284–11288.
- [44] F. Grieder, Virology, S. V, undefined. Role of Interferon and Interferon Regulatory Factors in Early Protection against Venezuelan Equine Encephalitis Virus Infection, Elsevier, 1999.
- [45] K.D. Ryman, W.B. Klimstra, K.B. Nguyen, C.A. Biron, R.E. Johnston, Alpha/beta interferon protects adult mice from fatal sindbis virus infection and is an important determinant of cell and tissue tropism, *J. Virol.* 74 (2000) 3366–3378.
- [46] T. Couderc, F. Chrétien, C. Schilte, O. Disson, M. Brigitte, A mouse model for Chikungunya infection: young age and inefficient type-I interferon signaling, *PLoS Pathog.* 4 (2008).
- [47] R.L. Seymour, S.L. Rossi, N.A. Bergren, K.S. Plante, S.C. Weaver, The role of innate versus adaptive immune responses in a mouse model of O'nyong-Nyong virus infection, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 88 (2013) 1170.
- [48] J.D. Morrey, et al., Effect of interferon-alpha and interferon-inducers on West Nile virus in mouse and hamster animal models, *Antivir. Chem. Chemother.* 15 (2004) 101–109.
- [49] T. Solomon, et al., Interferon alfa-2a in Japanese encephalitis: a randomised double-blind placebo-controlled trial, *Lancet (London, England)* 361 (2003) 821–826.
- [50] R.A. Lukaszewski, T.J.G. Brooks, Pegylated alpha interferon is an effective treatment for virulent Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus and has profound effects on the host immune response to infection, *J. Virol.* 74 (2000) 5006–5015.
- [51] M. Rodríguez-Pulido, et al., Protection against West Nile Virus Infection in Mice after Inoculation with Type I Interferon-Inducing RNA Transcripts, *PLoS One* 7 (2012).

- [52] K. Balz, L. Trassl, V. Härtel, P.P. Nelson, C. Skevaki, Virus-induced T Cell-mediated heterologous immunity and vaccine development, *Front. Immunol.* 11 (2020) 513.
- [53] Chumakov, K. et al. Old vaccines for new infections: Exploiting innate immunity to control COVID-19 and prevent future pandemics. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2101718118>.
- [54] J.B. Graham, et al., Immune correlates of protection from West Nile virus neuroinvasion and disease, *J. Infect. Dis.* 219 (2019) 1162–1171.
- [55] L.E. Yauch, et al., A protective role for dengue virus-specific CD8+ T cells, *J. Immunol.* 182 (2009) 4865–4873.
- [56] M.R. Bassi, et al., CD8+ T cells complement antibodies in protecting against yellow fever virus, *J. Immunol.* 194 (2015) 1141–1153.
- [57] M. Larena, M. Regner, E. Lee, M. Lobigs, Pivotal role of antibody and subsidiary contribution of CD8+ T cells to recovery from infection in a murine model of Japanese Encephalitis, *J. Virol.* 85 (2011) 5446.
- [58] L. Turtle, et al., Human T cell responses to Japanese encephalitis virus in health and disease, *J. Exp. Med.* 213 (2016) 1331–1352.
- [59] J.D. Brien, J.L. Uhrlaub, J. Nikolich-Zugich, West Nile virus-specific CD4 T cells exhibit direct antiviral cytokine secretion and cytotoxicity and are sufficient for antiviral protection, *J. Immunol.* 181 (2008) 8568–8575.
- [60] B. Shrestha, M.S. Diamond, Role of CD8 + T cells in control of west nile virus infection, *J. Virol.* 78 (2004) 8312–8321.
- [61] A. Elong Ngonon, et al., Mapping and role of the CD8 + T cell response during primary Zika virus infection in mice, *Cell Host Microbe* 21 (2017) 35–46.
- [62] N.M. Kafai, M.S. Diamond, J.M. Fox, Distinct Cellular Tropism and Immune Responses to Alphavirus Infection. doi:10.1146/annurev-immunol-101220-014952 40, 2022, pp. 615–649.
- [63] N.E. Yun, et al., CD4+ T cells provide protection against acute lethal encephalitis caused by Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus, *Vaccine* 27 (2009) 4064.
- [64] S. Paessler, et al., Alpha-beta T cells provide protection against lethal encephalitis in the murine model of VEEV infection, *Virology* 367 (2007) 307–323.
- [65] T.-H. Teo, et al., A pathogenic role for CD4 + T cells during chikungunya virus infection in mice, *J. Immunol.* 190 (2013) 259–269.
- [66] Y.S. Poo, et al., Multiple immune factors are involved in controlling acute and chronic chikungunya virus infection, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 8 (2014).
- [67] W.D. Crill, J.T. Roehrig, Monoclonal antibodies that bind to domain III of dengue virus E glycoprotein are the most efficient blockers of virus adsorption to Vero cells, *J. Virol.* 75 (2001) 7769–7773.
- [68] M.C. Kyung, et al., West Nile virus nonstructural protein NS1 inhibits complement activation by binding the regulatory protein factor H, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 103 (2006) 19111–19116.
- [69] K. Stiasny, S. Brandler, C. Kössl, F.X. Heinz, Probing the flavivirus membrane fusion mechanism by using monoclonal antibodies, *J. Virol.* 81 (2007) 11526.
- [70] E.A. Gould, A. Buckley, A.D.T. Barrett, N. Cammack, Neutralizing (54K) and non-neutralizing (54K and 48K) monoclonal antibodies against structural and non-structural yellow fever virus proteins confer immunity in mice, *J. Gen. Virol.* 67 (Pt 3) (1986) 591–595.
- [71] Y. Li, et al., Protective immunity to Japanese encephalitis virus associated with anti-NS1 antibodies in a mouse model, *Virol. J.* 9 (2012) 1–13.
- [72] J.R. Putnak, J.J. Schlesinger, Protection of mice against yellow fever virus encephalitis by immunization with a vaccinia virus recombinant encoding the yellow fever virus non-structural proteins, NS1, NS2a and NS2b, *J. Gen. Virol.* 71 (Pt 8) (1990) 1697–1702.
- [73] K.M. Chung, B.S. Thompson, D.H. Fremont, M.S. Diamond, Antibody recognition of cell surface-associated NS1 triggers Fc-gamma receptor-mediated phagocytosis and clearance of West Nile Virus-infected cells, *J. Virol.* 81 (2007) 9551–9555.
- [74] N. Modhiran, et al., A broadly protective antibody that targets the flavivirus NS1 protein, *Science* 371 (2021) 190–194.
- [75] L.A. Sanchez Vargas, et al., Non-structural protein 1-specific antibodies directed against Zika virus in humans mediate antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity, *Immunology* 164 (2021) 386–397.
- [76] S.B. Biering, et al., Structural basis for antibody inhibition of flavivirus NS1-triggered endothelial dysfunction, *Science* 371 (2021) 194–200.
- [77] R. de Alwis, et al., In-depth analysis of the antibody response of individuals exposed to primary dengue virus infection, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 5 (2011).
- [78] Y.W. Kam, et al., Unique epitopes recognized by antibodies induced in chikungunya virus-infected non-human primates: implications for the study of immunopathology and vaccine development, *PLoS One* 9 (2014).
- [79] I.K. Yoon, et al., High rate of subclinical chikungunya virus infection and association of neutralizing antibody with protection in a prospective cohort in the Philippines, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 9 (2015).
- [80] C.H. Calisher, et al., Antigenic relationships between flaviviruses as determined by cross-neutralization tests with polyclonal antisera, *J. Gen. Virol.* 70 (Pt 1) (1989) 37–43.
- [81] K.L. Mansfield, et al., Flavivirus-induced antibody cross-reactivity, *J. Gen. Virol.* 92 (2011) 2821–2829.
- [82] W.A.A. Saron, et al., Flavivirus serocomplex cross-reactive immunity is protective by activating heterologous memory CD4 T cells, *Sci. Adv.* 4 (2018).
- [83] J.L. Smith, et al., Human antibody responses to emerging mayaro virus and cocirculating alphavirus infections examined by using structural proteins from nine new and old world lineages, *mSphere* 3 (2018).
- [84] J. Jin, G. Simmons, Antiviral functions of monoclonal antibodies against Chikungunya virus, *Viruses* 11 (2019) 305.
- [85] L.A. Powell, et al., Human mAbs broadly protect against arthritogenic alphaviruses by recognizing conserved elements of the Mxra8 receptor-binding site, *Cell Host Microbe* 28 (2020) 699–711.e7.
- [86] J.M. Fox, et al., Broadly neutralizing alphavirus antibodies bind an epitope on E2 and inhibit entry and egress, *Cell* 163 (2015) 1095–1107.
- [87] A.S. Kim, et al., Pan-protective anti-alphavirus human antibodies target a conserved E1 protein epitope, *Cell* 184 (2021) 4414–4429.e19.
- [88] T.C. Pierson, D.H. Fremont, R.J. Kuhn, M.S. Diamond, Structural insights into the mechanisms of antibody-mediated neutralization of flavivirus infection: implications for vaccine development, *Cell Host Microbe* 4 (2008) 229–238.
- [89] M.H. Collins, et al., Lack of durable cross-neutralizing antibodies against Zika virus from dengue virus infection, *Emerg. Infect. Dis.* 23 (2017) 773–781.
- [90] M. Beltramello, et al., The human immune response to Dengue virus is dominated by highly cross-reactive antibodies endowed with neutralizing and enhancing activity, *Cell Host Microbe* 8 (2010) 271–283.
- [91] L.C. Katzelnick, et al., Antibody-dependent enhancement of severe dengue disease in humans, *Science* 358 (2017) 929–932.
- [92] S.V. Bardina, et al., Enhancement of Zika virus pathogenesis by preexisting anti-flavivirus immunity, *Science* 356 (2017) 175–180.
- [93] A.P.S. Rathore, W.A.A. Saron, T. Lim, N. Jahan, St. John, A. L., Maternal immunity and antibodies to dengue virus promote infection and Zika virus-induced microcephaly in fetuses, *Sci. Adv.* 5 (2019).
- [94] L.C. Katzelnick, S. Bos, E. Harris, Protective and enhancing interactions among dengue viruses 1-4 and Zika virus, *Curr. Opin. Virol.* 43 (2020) 59–70.
- [95] R. Khandia, et al., Modulation of dengue/zika virus pathogenicity by antibody-dependent enhancement and strategies to protect against enhancement in zika virus infection, *Front. Immunol.* 9 (2018) 1.
- [96] R. Kulkarni, Antibody-dependent enhancement of viral infections, *Dyn. Immune Act. Viral Dis.* 9 (2020), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1045-8_2.
- [97] A.B. Byrne, L.B. Talarico, Role of the complement system in antibody-dependent enhancement of flavivirus infections, *Int. J. Infect. Dis.* 103 (2021) 404–411.
- [98] C. Khou, N. Pardigon, Identifying attenuating mutations: tools for a new vaccine design against flaviviruses, *Intervirology* 60 (2017) 8–18.
- [99] L. Fiacre, et al., Molecular determinants of west nile virus virulence and pathogenesis in vertebrate and invertebrate hosts, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 21 (2020) 1–35.
- [100] M.V. Rangel, K.A. Stapleford, T. Mukhopadhyay, T. Morrison, Alphavirus virulence determinants, *Pathog.* 10 (2021) 981.
- [101] E.M. Kellman, D.K. Offerdahl, W. Melik, M.E. Bloom, Viral determinants of virulence in tick-borne flaviviruses, *Viruses* 10 (2018).
- [102] K. Szentpáli-Gavallér, et al., In vitro and in vivo evaluation of mutations in the NS region of lineage 2 west nile virus associated with neuroinvasiveness in a mammalian model, *Viruses* 8 (2016).
- [103] G.D. Gromowski, C.-Y. Firestone, S.S. Whitehead, Genetic determinants of japanese encephalitis virus vaccine strain SA14-14-2 that govern attenuation of virulence in mice, *J. Virol.* 89 (2015) 6328.
- [104] R. Gorchakov, et al., Attenuation of Chikungunya virus vaccine strain 181/clone 25 is determined by two amino acid substitutions in the E2 envelope glycoprotein, *J. Virol.* 86 (2012) 6084–6096.
- [105] K.D. Ryman, et al., Heparan sulfate binding can contribute to the neurovirulence of neuroadapted and nonneuroadapted Sindbis viruses, *J. Virol.* 81 (2007) 3563–3573.
- [106] E. Lee, M. Lobigs, Mechanism of virulence attenuation of glycosaminoglycan-binding variants of japanese encephalitis virus and murray valley encephalitis virus, *J. Virol.* 76 (2002) 4901–4911.
- [107] E. Lee, P.J. Wright, A. Davidson, M. Lobigs, Virulence attenuation of Dengue virus due to augmented glycosaminoglycan-binding affinity and restriction in extraneural dissemination, *J. Gen. Virol.* 87 (2006) 2791–2801.
- [108] L. Yang, et al., Substantial attenuation of virulence of tembusu virus strain PS is determined by an arginine at residue 304 of the envelope protein, *J. Virol.* 95 (2021).
- [109] K.A. Bernard, W.B. Klimstra, R.E. Johnston, Mutations in the E2 glycoprotein of Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus confer heparan sulfate interaction, low morbidity, and rapid clearance from blood of mice, *Virology* 276 (2000) 93–103.
- [110] C.L. Gardner, et al., Deliberate attenuation of chikungunya virus by adaptation to heparan sulfate-dependent infectivity: a model for rational avoviral vaccine design, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 8 (2014).
- [111] X. Wang, et al., Near-atomic structure of Japanese encephalitis virus reveals critical determinants of virulence and stability, *Nat. Commun.* 8 (2017).
- [112] C.L. Gardner, G.D. Ebel, K.D. Ryman, W.B. Klimstra, Heparan sulfate binding by natural eastern equine encephalitis viruses promotes neurovirulence, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 108 (2011) 16026–16031.
- [113] J. Arroyo, et al., ChimeriVax-west nile virus live-attenuated vaccine: preclinical evaluation of safety, immunogenicity, and efficacy, *J. Virol.* 78 (2004) 12497–12507.
- [114] S. Zhang, et al., A mutation in the envelope protein fusion loop attenuates mouse neuroinvasiveness of the NY99 strain of West Nile virus, *Virology* 353 (2006) 35–40.
- [115] D.L. Carbaugh, H.M. Lazear, Flavivirus envelope protein glycosylation: impacts on viral infection and pathogenesis, *J. Virol.* 94 (2020).
- [116] Y.D. Gwon, E. Zusinaite, A. Merits, A.K. Överby, M. Evander, N-glycosylation in the pre-membrane protein is essential for the Zika virus life cycle, *Viruses* 12 (2020).
- [117] K.L. Carpio, A.D.T. Barrett, Flavivirus NS1 and its potential in vaccine development, *Vaccines* 9 (2021).
- [118] M.A. Nelson, et al., Role of envelope N-linked glycosylation in Ross River virus virulence and transmission, *J. Gen. Virol.* 97 (2016) 1094–1106.

- [119] R.L. Knight, K.L.W. Schultz, R.J. Kent, M. Venkatesan, D.E. Griffin, Role of N-linked glycosylation for sindbis virus infection and replication in vertebrate and invertebrate systems, *J. Virol.* 83 (2009) 5640–5647.
- [120] J.J. Liang, M.W. Chou, Y.L. Lin, DC-SIGN binding contributed by an extra n-linked glycosylation on Japanese encephalitis virus envelope protein reduces the ability of viral brain invasion, *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* 8 (2018).
- [121] D.W.C. Beasley, et al., Envelope protein glycosylation status influences mouse neuroinvasion phenotype of genetic lineage 1 West Nile virus strains, *J. Virol.* 79 (2005) 8339–8347.
- [122] W. Yang Zhu, et al., Effects of the nsP2-726 Pro mutation on infectivity and pathogenesis of Sindbis virus derived from a full-length infectious cDNA clone, *Virus Res.* 142 (2009) 204–207.
- [123] Y. Zhou, et al., Structure and function of flavivirus NS5 methyltransferase, *J. Virol.* 81 (2007) 3891–3903.
- [124] J.J. Fros, et al., Chikungunya virus nonstructural protein 2 inhibits Type I/II interferon-stimulated JAK-STAT signaling, *J. Virol.* 84 (2010) 10877–10887.
- [125] G.P. Pijlman, et al., A Highly structured, nuclease-resistant, noncoding RNA produced by flaviviruses is required for pathogenicity, *Cell Host Microbe* 4 (2008) 579–591.
- [126] J. Bustos-Arriaga, et al., Decreased accumulation of subgenomic RNA in human cells infected with vaccine candidate DEN4Δ30 increases viral susceptibility to type I interferon, *Vaccine* 36 (2018) 3460–3467.
- [127] J.E. Blaney, A.P. Durbin, B.R. Murphy, S.S. Whitehead, Development of a live attenuated dengue virus vaccine using reverse genetics, *Viral Immunol.* 19 (2006) 10–32.
- [128] E.G. Chapman, et al., The structural basis of pathogenic subgenomic flavivirus RNA (sfRNA) production, *Science* (80-.). 344 (2014) 307–310.
- [129] A. Funk, et al., RNA structures required for production of subgenomic flavivirus RNA, *J. Virol.* 84 (2010) 11407–11417.
- [130] G.P. Göertz, et al., Subgenomic flavivirus RNA binds the mosquito DEAD/H-box helicase ME31B and determines Zika virus transmission by *Aedes aegypti*, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 116 (2019) 19136–19144.
- [131] S.-C. Yeh, J. Pompon, Flaviviruses produce a subgenomic flavivirus RNA that enhances mosquito transmission, *DNA Cell Biol.* 37 (2018) 154–159.
- [132] J. Pompon, et al., Dengue subgenomic flavivirus RNA disrupts immunity in mosquito salivary glands to increase virus transmission, *PLoS Pathog.* 13 (2017), e1006535.
- [133] A. Slonchak, et al., Zika virus noncoding RNA suppresses apoptosis and is required for virus transmission by mosquitoes, *Nat. Commun.* 11 (11) (2020) 1–14.
- [134] G.P. Göertz, et al., Noncoding subgenomic flavivirus RNA is processed by the mosquito rna interference machinery and determines west nile virus transmission by *Culex pipiens* mosquitoes, *J. Virol.* 90 (2016) 10145–10159.
- [135] T.F. Kautz, N.L. Forrester, RNA virus fidelity mutants: a useful tool for evolutionary biology or a complex challenge? *Viruses* 10 (2018).
- [136] E.H. Davis, et al., Japanese encephalitis virus live attenuated vaccine strains display altered immunogenicity, virulence and genetic diversity, *npj Vaccin.* 6 (2021) 1–14.
- [137] J.A. Kaiser, et al., Japanese encephalitis vaccine-specific envelope protein E138K mutation does not attenuate virulence of West Nile virus, *NPJ Vaccin.* 4 (2019).
- [138] J.-M. Kim, et al., A single N-linked glycosylation site in the Japanese encephalitis virus prM protein is critical for cell type-specific prM protein biogenesis, virus particle release, and pathogenicity in mice, *J. Virol.* 82 (2008) 7846–7862.
- [139] A.S. Annamalai, et al., Zika virus encoding nonglycosylated envelope protein is attenuated and defective in neuroinvasion, *J. Virol.* 91 (2017).
- [140] N.A. Prow, et al., Determinants of attenuation in the envelope protein of the flavivirus Alfuy, *J. Gen. Virol.* 92 (2011) 2286–2296.
- [141] K. Yoshii, N. Yanagihara, M. Ishizuka, M. Sakai, H. Kariwa, N-linked glycan in tick-borne encephalitis virus envelope protein affects viral secretion in mammalian cells, but not in tick cells, *J. Gen. Virol.* 94 (2013) 2249–2258.
- [142] D. Liu, et al., Glycosylation on envelope glycoprotein of duck Tembusu virus affects virus replication in vitro and contributes to the neurovirulence and pathogenicity in vivo, *Virulence* 12 (2021) 2400–2414.
- [143] E. Lee, R.A. Hall, M. Lobigs, Common E protein determinants for attenuation of glycosaminoglycan-binding variants of Japanese encephalitis and west nile viruses, *J. Virol.* 78 (2004) 8271–8280.
- [144] E. Lee, M. Lobigs, E Protein domain III determinants of yellow fever virus 17D vaccine strain enhance binding to glycosaminoglycans, impede virus spread, and attenuate virulence, *J. Virol.* 82 (2008) 6024–6033.
- [145] E. Lee, P.J. Wright, A. Davidson, M. Lobigs, Virulence attenuation of Dengue virus due to augmented glycosaminoglycan-binding affinity and restriction in extraneural dissemination, *J. Gen. Virol.* 87 (2006) 2791–2801.
- [146] E. Lee, M. Lobigs, Substitutions at the putative receptor-binding site of an encephalitic flavivirus alter virulence and host cell tropism and reveal a role for glycosaminoglycans in entry, *J. Virol.* 74 (2000) 8867–8875.
- [147] A. Goto, et al., Role of the N-linked glycans of the prM and E envelope proteins in tick-borne encephalitis virus particle secretion, *Vaccine* 23 (2005) 3043–3052.
- [148] C.W. Mandl, et al., Adaptation of tick-borne encephalitis virus to BHK-21 cells results in the formation of multiple heparan sulfate binding sites in the envelope protein and attenuation in vivo, *J. Virol.* 75 (2001) 5627–5637.
- [149] L. Yang, et al., Substantial attenuation of virulence of tembusu virus strain Ps is determined by an arginine at residue 304 of the envelope protein, *J. Virol.* 95 (2021).
- [150] J. Arroyo, et al., ChimeriVax-west nile virus live-attenuated vaccine: preclinical evaluation of safety, immunogenicity, and efficacy, *J. Virol.* 78 (2004) 12497–12507.
- [151] M.B. Crabtree, R.M. Kinney, B.R. Miller, Deglycosylation of the NS1 protein of dengue 2 virus, strain 16681: construction and characterization of mutant viruses, *Arch. Virol.* 150 (2005) 771–786.
- [152] I.R. Muijlaert, T.J. Chambers, R. Galler, C.M. Rice, Mutagenesis of the N-linked glycosylation sites of the yellow fever virus NS1 protein: Effects on virus replication and mouse neurovirulence, *Virology* 222 (1996) 159–168.
- [153] M.C. Whiteman, et al., Multiple amino acid changes at the first glycosylation motif in NS1 protein of West Nile virus are necessary for complete attenuation for mouse neuroinvasiveness, *Vaccine* 29 (2011) 9702–9710.
- [154] S.-H. Li, et al., Rational design of a flavivirus vaccine by abolishing viral RNA 2'-O methylation, *J. Virol.* 87 (2013) 5812–5819.
- [155] C. Shan, et al., A live-attenuated Zika virus vaccine candidate induces sterilizing immunity in mouse models, *Nat. Med.* 236 (23) (2017) 763–767.
- [156] J.E. Blaney, et al., Dengue virus type 3 vaccine candidates generated by introduction of deletions in the 3' untranslated region (3'-UTR) or by exchange of the DENV-3 3'-UTR with that of DENV-4, *Vaccine* 26 (2008) 817–828.
- [157] C.L. Gardner, et al., Deliberate attenuation of chikungunya virus by adaptation to heparan sulfate-dependent infectivity: a model for rational arboviral vaccine design, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 8 (2014).
- [158] M.C. Ferguson, et al., Ability of the encephalitic arbovirus semliki forest virus to cross the blood-brain barrier is determined by the charge of the E2 glycoprotein, *J. Virol.* 89 (2015) 7536–7549.
- [159] N.L. Davis, F.J. Fuller, W.G. Dougherty, R.A. Olmsted, R.E. Johnston, A single nucleotide change in the E2 glycoprotein gene of Sindbis virus affects penetration rate in cell culture and virulence in neonatal mice, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 83 (1986) 6771–6775.
- [160] J.E. Jones, et al., Disruption of the opal stop codon attenuates chikungunya virus-induced arthritis and pathology, *MBio* 8 (2017).
- [161] M.S. Suthar, R. Shabman, K. Madric, C. Lambeth, M.T. Heise, Identification of adult mouse neurovirulence determinants of the Sindbis virus strain AR86, *J. Virol.* 79 (2005) 4219–4228.
- [162] M. Tuittila, A.E. Hinkkanen, Amino acid mutations in the replicase protein nsP3 of Semliki Forest virus cumulatively affect neurovirulence, *J. Gen. Virol.* 84 (2003) 1525–1533.
- [163] T. Ishikawa, A. Yamanaka, E. Konishi, A review of successful flavivirus vaccines and the problems with those flaviviruses for which vaccines are not yet available, *Vaccine* 32 (2014) 1326–1337.
- [164] M. Giel-Moloney, et al., Chimeric yellow fever 17D-Zika virus (ChimeriVax-Zika) as a live-attenuated Zika virus vaccine, *Sci. Report.* 81 (8) (2018) 1–11.
- [165] B. Guy, et al., Preclinical and clinical development of YFV 17D-based chimeric vaccines against dengue, West Nile and Japanese encephalitis viruses, *Vaccine* 28 (2010) 632–649.
- [166] S. Halstead, diseases, S. T.-C. infectious, undefined. Japanese encephalitis: new options for active immunization, *academic.oup.com* 50 (2010) 1155–1164.
- [167] R. Biedebender, J. Bevilacqua, A.M. Gregg, M. Watson, G. Dayan, Phase II, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter study to investigate the immunogenicity and safety of a west nile virus vaccine in healthy adults, *J. Infect. Dis.* 203 (2011) 75–84.
- [168] D.B. Kum, et al., A chimeric yellow fever-Zika virus vaccine candidate fully protects against yellow fever virus infection in mice, *Emerg. Microbes Infect.* 9 (2020) 520.
- [169] S.J. Thomas, I.K. Yoon, A review of Dengvaxia®: development to deployment, *Hum. Vaccin. Immunother.* 15 (2019) 2295–2314.
- [170] S. Henein, et al., Dengue vaccine breakthrough infections reveal properties of neutralizing antibodies linked to protection, *J. Clin. Invest.* 131 (2021).
- [171] C.Y.H. Huang, et al., Genetic and phenotypic characterization of manufacturing seeds for a tetravalent dengue vaccine (DENVax), *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 7 (2013), e2243.
- [172] C. Sirivichayakul, et al., Safety and immunogenicity of a tetravalent dengue vaccine candidate in healthy children and adults in dengue-endemic regions: a randomized, placebo-controlled phase 2 study, *J. Infect. Dis.* 213 (2016) 1562–1572.
- [173] L. Rivera, et al., Three-year efficacy and safety of takeda's dengue vaccine candidate (TAK-003), *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 75 (2022) 107–117.
- [174] S.L. George, et al., Safety and immunogenicity of a live attenuated tetravalent dengue vaccine candidate in flavivirus-naive adults: a randomized, double-blinded phase 1 clinical trial, *J. Infect. Dis.* 212 (2015) 1032–1041.
- [175] L.A. Jackson, et al., A phase 1 study of safety and immunogenicity following intradermal administration of a tetravalent dengue vaccine candidate, *Vaccine* 36 (2018) 3976–3983.
- [176] W.R. Baldwin, et al., Single dose of chimeric dengue-2/Zika vaccine candidate protects mice and non-human primates against Zika virus, *Nat. Commun.* 121 (12) (2021) 1–15.
- [177] C.Y.-H. Huang, S.J. Silengo, M.C. Whiteman, R.M. Kinney, Chimeric dengue 2 PDK-53/West Nile NY99 viruses retain the phenotypic attenuation markers of the candidate PDK-53 vaccine virus and protect mice against lethal challenge with West Nile virus, *J. Virol.* 79 (2005) 7300–7310.
- [178] S.S. Whitehead, Development of TV003/TV005, a single dose, highly immunogenic live attenuated dengue vaccine; what makes this vaccine different from the Sanofi-Pasteur CYD™ vaccine? 15 (2015) 509–517, <https://doi.org/10.1586/14760584.2016.1115727>.
- [179] B.D. Kirkpatrick, et al., Robust and balanced immune responses to All 4 dengue virus serotypes following administration of a single dose of a live attenuated tetravalent dengue vaccine to healthy, flavivirus-naive adults, *J. Infect. Dis.* 212 (2015) 702–710.

- [180] J.U. Galula, G.M. Salem, G.J.J. Chang, D.Y. Chao, Does structurally-mature dengue virion matter in vaccine preparation in post-Dengvaxia era? 15, 2019, pp. 2328–2336, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645515.2019.1643676>.
- [181] X.F. Li, et al., Development of a chimeric Zika vaccine using a licensed live-attenuated flavivirus vaccine as backbone, *Nat. Commun.* 91 (9) (2018) 1–11.
- [182] S. Paessler, et al., Recombinant sindbis/Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus is highly attenuated and immunogenic, *J. Virol.* 77 (2003) 9278–9286.
- [183] S. Paessler, et al., Replication and clearance of Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus from the brains of animals vaccinated with Chimeric SIN/VEE viruses, *J. Virol.* 80 (2006) 2784–2796.
- [184] E. Wang, et al., Chimeric alphavirus vaccine candidates for chikungunya, *Vaccine* 26 (2008) 5030.
- [185] R.J. Schoepp, J.F. Smith, M.D. Parker, Recombinant chimeric western and eastern equine encephalitis viruses as potential vaccine candidates, *Virology* 302 (2002) 299–309.
- [186] S. Junglen, C. Drosten, Virus discovery and recent insights into virus diversity in arthropods, *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.* 16 (2013) 507–513.
- [187] N. Vasilakis, R.B. Tesh, Insect-specific viruses and their potential impact on arbovirus transmission, *Curr. Opin. Virol.* 15 (2015) 69–74.
- [188] E. Huhtamo, et al., Novel flaviviruses from mosquitoes: Mosquito-specific evolutionary lineages within the phylogenetic group of mosquito-borne flaviviruses, *Virology* 464–465 (2014) 320.
- [189] A.M.G. Colmant, et al., Insect-specific flavivirus replication in mammalian cells is inhibited by physiological temperature and the zinc-finger antiviral protein, *Viruses* 13 (2021) 573.
- [190] J.H. Erasmus, et al., A chikungunya fever vaccine utilizing an insect-specific virus platform, *Nat. Med.* 23 (2017) 192–199.
- [191] J.J. Harrison, J. Hobson-Peters, H. Bielefeldt-Ohmann, R.A. Hall, Chimeric vaccines based on novel insect-specific flaviviruses, *Vaccines* 9 (2021) 1230.
- [192] T.B.H. Piyasena, et al., Chimeric viruses of the insect-specific flavivirus Palm Creek with structural proteins of vertebrate-infecting flaviviruses identify barriers to replication of insect-specific flaviviruses in vertebrate cells, *J. Gen. Virol.* 100 (2019) 1580–1586.
- [193] J. Hobson-Peters, et al., A recombinant platform for flavivirus vaccines and diagnostics using chimeras of a new insect-specific virus, *Sci. Transl. Med.* 11 (2019) 7888.
- [194] E.R. Gaunt, P. Digard, Compositional biases in RNA viruses: Causes, consequences and applications, *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. RNA* e1679 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1002/WRNA.1679>.
- [195] B. Irwin, J.D. Heck, G.W. Hatfield, Codon pair utilization biases influence translational elongation step times, *J. Biol. Chem.* 270 (1995) 22801–22806.
- [196] Y. Liu, A code within the genetic code: Codon usage regulates co-translational protein folding, *Cell Commun. Signal.* 18 (2020) 1–9.
- [197] C.E. Brule, E.J. Grayhack, Synonymous codons: choose wisely for expression, *Trends Genet.* 33 (2017) 283.
- [198] A. Nougairède, et al., Random codon re-encoding induces stable reduction of replicative fitness of chikungunya virus in primate and mosquito cells, *PLoS Pathog.* 9 (2013), e1003172.
- [199] G. Manokaran, Sujatmoko, K.G. McPherson, C.P. Simmons, Attenuation of a dengue virus replicon by codon deoptimization of nonstructural genes, *Vaccine* 37 (2019) 2857–2863.
- [200] P. Li, et al., Zika virus attenuation by codon pair deoptimization induces sterilizing immunity in mouse models, *J. Virol.* 92 (2018).
- [201] S.H. Shen, et al., Large-scale recoding of an arbovirus genome to rebalance its insect versus mammalian preference, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 112 (2015) 4749–4754.
- [202] C.B. Stauff, et al., Extensive genomic recoding by codon-pair deoptimization selective for mammals is a flexible tool to generate attenuated vaccine candidates for dengue virus 2, *Virology* 537 (2019) 237–245.
- [203] L. Carrau, et al., Chikungunya virus vaccine candidates with decreased mutational robustness are attenuated in vivo and have compromised transmissibility, *J. Virol.* 93 (2019).
- [204] L. de Fabritius, A. Nougairède, F. Aubry, E.A. Gould, X. de Lamballerie, Attenuation of tick-borne encephalitis virus using large-scale random codon re-encoding, *PLoS Pathog.* 11 (2015), e1004738.
- [205] L. Velazquez-Salinas, et al., Selective factors associated with the evolution of codon usage in natural populations of arboviruses, *PLoS One* 11 (2016), e0159943.
- [206] F. Tulloch, N.J. Atkinson, D.J. Evans, M.D. Ryan, P. Simmonds, RNA virus attenuation by codon pair deoptimisation is an artefact of increases in CpG/UpA dinucleotide frequencies, *Elife* 3 (2014), e04531.
- [207] B.K. Rima, N.V. McFerran, Dinucleotide and stop codon frequencies in single-stranded RNA viruses, *J. Gen. Virol.* 78 (1997) 2859–2870.
- [208] D. Kunec, N. Osterrieder, Codon pair bias is a direct consequence of dinucleotide bias, *Cell Rep.* 14 (2016) 55–67.
- [209] G.M. Jenkins, E.C. Holmes, The extent of codon usage bias in human RNA viruses and its evolutionary origin, *Virus Res.* 92 (2003) 1–7.
- [210] P. Simmonds, W. Xia, J.K. Baillie, K. McKinnon, Modelling mutational and selection pressures on dinucleotides in eukaryotic phyla -selection against CpG and UpA in cytoplasmically expressed RNA and in RNA viruses, *BMC Genomics* 14 (2013) 610.
- [211] F. Di Giallonardo, T.E. Schlub, M. Shi, E.C. Holmes, Dinucleotide composition in animal RNA viruses is shaped more by virus family than by host species, *J. Virol.* 91 (2017).
- [212] J.J. Fros, et al., The dinucleotide composition of the Zika virus genome is shaped by conflicting evolutionary pressures in mammalian hosts and mosquito vectors, *PLoS Biol.* 19 (2021), e3001201.
- [213] I. Trus, et al., CpG-recoding in Zika virus genome causes host-age-dependent attenuation of infection with protection against lethal heterologous challenge in mice, *Front. Immunol.* 10 (2020) 3077.
- [214] N.R. Sexton, G.D. Ebel, Effects of arbovirus multi-host life cycles on dinucleotide and codon usage patterns, *Viruses* 11 (2019).
- [215] X. Guo, J.-W.N. Carroll, M.R. MacDonald, S.P. Goff, G. Gao, The zinc finger antiviral protein directly binds to specific viral mRNAs through the CCCH zinc finger motifs, *J. Virol.* 78 (2004) 12781–12787.
- [216] V. Odon, et al., The role of ZAP and OAS3/RNaseL pathways in the attenuation of an RNA virus with elevated frequencies of CpG and UpA dinucleotides, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 47 (2019) 8061–8083.
- [217] M.A. Takata, et al., CG dinucleotide suppression enables antiviral defence targeting non-self RNA, *Nature* 550 (2017) 124–127.
- [218] M. Ficarella, et al., KHNYN is essential for the zinc finger antiviral protein (ZAP) to restrict HIV-1 containing clustered CpG dinucleotides, *Elife* 8 (2019).
- [219] H.P. Chiu, et al., Inhibition of Japanese encephalitis virus infection by the host zinc-finger antiviral protein, *PLoS Pathog.* 14 (2018).
- [220] Y. Zhu, X. Wang, S.P. Goff, G. Gao, Translational repression precedes and is required for ZAP-mediated mRNA decay, *EMBO J.* 31 (2012) 4236–4246.
- [221] J.L. Meagher, et al., Structure of the zinc-finger antiviral protein in complex with RNA reveals a mechanism for selective targeting of CG-rich viral sequences, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 116 (2019) 24303–24309.
- [222] M.J. Bick, et al., Expression of the zinc-finger antiviral protein inhibits alphavirus replication, *J. Virol.* 77 (2003) 11555–11562.
- [223] V. Choumet, et al., Visualizing non-infectious and infectious anopheles gambiae blood feedings in naive and saliva-immunized mice, *PLoS One* 7 (2012), e50464.
- [224] L.M. Styer, et al., Mosquitoes inoculate high doses of West Nile virus as they probe and feed on live hosts, *PLoS Pathog.* 3 (2007) 1262–1270.
- [225] L.M. Styer, et al., Mosquito saliva causes enhancement of west Nile virus infection in mice, *J. Virol.* 85 (2011) 1517–1527.
- [226] M. Pingen, M.A. Schmid, E. Harris, C.S. McKimmie, Mosquito biting modulates skin response to virus infection, *Trends Parasitol.* 33 (2017) 645–657.
- [227] S. Thangamani, et al., Host immune response to mosquito-transmitted chikungunya virus differs from that elicited by needle inoculated virus, *PLoS One* 5 (2010), e12137.
- [228] B.S. Schneider, L. Soong, N.S. Zeidner, S. Higgs, Aedes aegypti salivary gland extracts modulate anti-viral and T H1/TH2 cytokine responses to sindbis virus infection, *Viral Immunol.* 17 (2004) 565–573.
- [229] A. Agarwal, et al., Mosquito saliva induced cutaneous events augment Chikungunya virus replication and disease progression, *Infect. Genet. Evol.* 40 (2016) 126–135.
- [230] J.F. Edwards, S. Higgs, B.J. Beaty, Mosquito feeding-induced enhancement of cache valley virus (Bunyaviridae) infection in mice, *J. Med. Entomol.* 35 (1998) 261–265.
- [231] M.A. Schmid, et al., Mosquito saliva increases endothelial permeability in the skin, immune cell migration, and dengue pathogenesis during antibody-dependent enhancement, *PLoS Pathog.* 12 (2016), e1005676.
- [232] B.S. Schneider, et al., Potentiation of West Nile encephalitis by mosquito feeding, *Viral Immunol.* 19 (2006) 74–82.
- [233] C. Machain-Williams, K. Reagan, T. Wang, N.S. Zeidner, C.D. Blair, Immunization with culex tarsalis mosquito salivary gland extract modulates west Nile virus infection and disease in mice, *Viral Immunol.* 26 (2013) 84–92.
- [234] R. Uraki, A.K. Hastings, D.E. Brackney, P.M. Armstrong, E. Fikrig, AgBR1 antibodies delay lethal Aedes aegypti-borne West Nile virus infection in mice, *npj Vaccin.* 4 (2019) 1–4.
- [235] Y. Wang, A. Marin-Lopez, J. Jiang, M. Ledizet, E. Fikrig, Vaccination with aedes aegypti AgBR1 delays lethal mosquito-borne Zika virus infection in mice, *Vaccines* 8 (2020).
- [236] A.K. Hastings, et al., Aedes aegypti NeSt1 protein enhances Zika virus pathogenesis by activating neutrophils, *J. Virol.* 93 (2019).
- [237] A. Marin-Lopez, Y. Wang, J. Jiang, M. Ledizet, E. Fikrig, AgBR1 and NeSt1 antisera protect mice from Aedes aegypti-borne Zika infection, *Vaccine* 39 (2021) 1675–1679.
- [238] M.J. Conway, et al., Aedes aegypti D7 saliva protein inhibits dengue virus infection, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 10 (2016), e0004941.
- [239] K.L. Reagan, C. Machain-Williams, T. Wang, C.D. Blair, Immunization of mice with recombinant mosquito salivary protein D7 enhances mortality from subsequent west Nile virus infection via mosquito bite, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 6 (2012), e1935.
- [240] F. Oliveira, P.G. Lawyer, S. Kamhawi, J.G. Valenzuela, Immunity to distinct sand fly salivary proteins primes the anti-leishmania immune response towards protection or exacerbation of disease, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2 (2008).
- [241] S. Kamhawi, Y. Belkaid, G. Modi, E. Rowton, D. Sacks, Protection against cutaneous leishmaniasis resulting from bites of uninfected sand flies, *Science* 290 (2000) 1351–1354.
- [242] R. Gomes, et al., Immunity to a salivary protein of a sand fly vector protects against the fatal outcome of visceral leishmaniasis in a hamster model, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 105 (2008) 7845–7850.
- [243] A. Sajid, et al., mRNA vaccination induces tick resistance and prevents transmission of the Lyme disease agent, *Sci. Transl. Med.* 13 (2021).
- [244] F. Oliveira, et al., A sand fly salivary protein vaccine shows efficacy against vector-transmitted cutaneous leishmaniasis in nonhuman primates, *Sci. Transl. Med.* 7 (2015).

- [245] J.E. Manning, et al., Safety and immunogenicity of a mosquito saliva peptide-based vaccine: a randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind, phase 1 trial, *Lancet* 395 (2020) 1998–2007.
- [246] R.L. Coffman, A. Sher, R.A. Seder, Vaccine adjuvants: Putting innate immunity to work, *Immunity* 33 (2010) 492–503.
- [247] Z. Peng, F.R. Simons, A prospective study of naturally acquired sensitization and subsequent desensitization to mosquito bites and concurrent antibody responses, *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 101 (1998) 284–286.
- [248] J.E. Manning, et al., Development of inapparent dengue associated with increased antibody levels to aedes aegypti salivary proteins: a longitudinal dengue cohort in Cambodia, *J. Infect. Dis.* XX (2021) 1–11.
- [249] F. Zahedifard, et al., Enhanced protective efficacy of nonpathogenic recombinant leishmania tarentolae expressing cysteine proteinases combined with a sand fly salivary antigen, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 8 (2014), e2751.
- [250] B.D. Gastfriend, S.P. Palecek, E.V. Shusta, Modeling the blood–brain barrier: Beyond the endothelial cells, *Curr. Opin. Biomed. Eng.* 5 (2018) 6–12.
- [251] M. Chesnut, et al., In vitro and in silico models to study mosquito-borne flavivirus neuropathogenesis, prevention, and treatment, *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.* 9 (2019) 223.
- [252] A.T. Esterly, M.G. Lloyd, P. Upadhyaya, J.F. Moffat, S. Thangamani, A human skin model for assessing arboviral infections, *JID Innov.* 2 (2022), 100128.
- [253] F. Groell, O. Jordan, G. Borchard, In vitro models for immunogenicity prediction of therapeutic proteins, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 130 (2018) 128–142.
- [254] P. Rosenbaum, et al., Vaccine inoculation route modulates early immunity and consequently antigen-specific immune response, *Front. Immunol.* 12 (2021) 1362.
- [255] S. Ols, et al., Route of vaccine administration alters antigen trafficking but not innate or adaptive immunity, *Cell Rep.* 30 (2020) 3964–3971.e7.
- [256] M.J. Turell, M.D. Parker, Protection of hamsters by Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus candidate vaccine V3526 against lethal challenge by mosquito bite and intraperitoneal injection, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 78 (2008) 328–332.
- [257] B.S. Davis, et al., West Nile virus recombinant DNA vaccine protects mouse and horse from virus challenge and expresses in vitro a noninfectious recombinant antigen that can be used in enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays, *J. Virol.* 75 (2001) 4040–4047.
- [258] K. Karaca, et al., Recombinant canarypox vectored West Nile virus (WNV) vaccine protects dogs and cats against a mosquito WNV challenge, *Vaccine* 23 (2005) 3808–3813.
- [259] J.M. Minke, et al., Recombinant canarypoxvirus vaccine carrying the prM/E genes of West Nile virus protects horses against a West Nile virus-mosquito challenge, *Arch. Virol. Suppl.* 221–230 (2004), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7091-0572-6_20.
- [260] R.C. Christofferson, M.K. McCracken, A.M. Johnson, D.M. Chisenhall, C.N. Mores, Development of a transmission model for dengue virus, *Virol. J.* 10 (2013) 127.
- [261] D.M. Dudley, et al., Infection via mosquito bite alters Zika virus tissue tropism and replication kinetics in rhesus macaques, *Nat. Commun.* 8 (2017).
- [262] M.K. McCracken, et al., Route of inoculation and mosquito vector exposure modulate dengue virus replication kinetics and immune responses in rhesus macaques, *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 14 (2020), e0008191.
- [263] J.E. Osorio, M.S. Godsey, G.R. Defoliart, T.M. La Yuill, cross viremia in white-tailed deer and chipmunks exposed by injection or mosquito bite, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 54 (1996) 338–342.
- [264] J.A. Vaughan, L.F. Scheller, R.A. Wirtz, A.F. Azad, Infectivity of Plasmodium berghei sporozoites delivered by intravenous inoculation versus mosquito bite: Implications for sporozoite vaccine trials, *Infect. Immun.* 67 (1999) 4285–4289.
- [265] N.C. Peters, et al., Vector transmission of leishmania abrogates vaccine-induced protective immunity, *PLoS Pathog.* 5 (2009), e1000484.
- [266] J.D. Watson, F.H.C. Crick, Molecular structure of nucleic acids: a structure for deoxyribose nucleic acid, *Nat.* 1714356 (171) (1953) 737–738.
- [267] A.S. Lauring, J.O. Jones, R. Andino, Rationalizing the development of live attenuated virus vaccines, *Nat. Biotechnol.* 28 (2010) 573–579.
- [268] J. Arroyo, et al., Molecular basis for attenuation of neurovirulence of a yellow fever virus/Japanese encephalitis virus chimera vaccine (ChimeriVax-JE), *J. Virol.* 75 (2001) 934–942.